

Studies on the Use of meta-Periodic Acid as an Oxidant for the Estimation of Dihydroxy Acetone (dimer) and Investigation of Reaction-Mechanism

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Dihydroxyacetone has been estimated by meta-periodic acid within a time limit of 2 hrs at 25° at pH ~ 8. The reaction has been shown to be of second order which appeared to be fastest at pH ~ 10 and on both sides of this value, the rate appeared to slow down. It has been shown that the reaction takes place between dihydroxy acetone molecule and periodate ion. The temperature co-efficient was found to be of the order of 2.15 for the temperature range 35–40° and the energy of activation was 31.92 K.cals. at pH ~ 2.

Some work on the estimation of dihydroxy-acetone has been reported¹ and no work seems to have been done on the kinetics of the oxidation of dihydroxyacetone by periodic acid. The present investigation has been undertaken to determine the conditions for stoichiometry of the reaction of dihydroxy-acetone with periodate and to study its reaction mechanism.

The reaction takes place as follows—

TABLE I

No.	Dihydroxy acetone (dimer) present gms.	Dihydroxy acetone (dimer) found gms.	% Recovery	% Error ±
1.	0.00375	0.00376	100.26	+0.26
2.	0.00600	0.00601	100.17	+0.17
3.	0.00750	0.00750	100.00	±0.00
4.	0.00900	0.00902	100.22	+0.22

Kinetic study of the reaction between dihydroxy acetone and meta-periodic acid: The procedure adopted was the same as given earlier in cases of tartaric acid² and Mandelic acid³.

1. Fleury and Lange, *J. Pharm. Chem.*, 1933, **17**, 409.
2. P. S. Verma and K. C. Grover, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1968, **21**, 1531.
3. P. S. Verma and K. C. Grover, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**(2), 141.

Reaction Rates : Graphs were plotted for all results and the specific rate constants k_1 (first order) (figure I) and k_2 (second order) (figures II and III) obtained from the slope of $\log(a-x)$ and $1/(a-x)$ respectively against time. The value of k_2 thus obtained is then multiplied by a factor V/S when "V" is the volume of the reaction mixture analysed every time (here, 10 ml.) and "S" is the strength of the iodine solution, this is the absolute value of K_2 . In all graphs "a" stands for the amount of periodate taken and "X" for periodate consumed in terms of the titre values of 0.005 N iodine solution (with which the final titrations were carried out).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In case of studies using excess of periodate at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ graphs were plotted of the values of $\log(a-x)$ vs time in minutes (figure I) and a straight line was obtained. From the slope, the value of k_1 was calculated and found to be $2.00 \times 10^{-1} \text{ min.}^{-1}$. The above result showed that the order of the reaction with respect to dihydroxyacetone is one. The corresponding

study with respect to periodate could not be conducted due to analytical difficulties. The over all order of reaction was found to be two, which was confirmed by the results obtained on studies of second order constants using equivalent concentrations of reactants (figures II and III) where the straight line was obtained by plotting the value of $1/(a-x)$ against time

in minutes. The temperature coefficient was found to be of the order of 2.15 for the temperature range 35–40° and energy of activation was 31.92 K.cals/mole at pH ~ 2. The studies on the effect of addition of sulphate ions (figure IIB) and acetate ions (figure IIC)

showed that there is an inhibiting effect on the addition of sulphate and acetate ions. Besides at pH 4 and 6 as well as 50% N.N. dimethyl formamide as solvent no reaction seemed to take place within a reasonable interval of time.

TABLE II(A)

Second order constants at 35 ± 0.1°

(Effect of addition of ions)

pH	Periodate	Dihydroxy-acetone (dimer)	Curve	(min. ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹ litre)
1.94	3.125 × 10 ⁻³	1.04 × 10 ⁻³	A	1.84
1.95	"	"	B	0.56 (in presence of SO ₄ ⁻)
1.85	"	"	C	0.92 (In presence of CH ₃ COO ⁻)

TABLE II(B)

Second order constants at 35 ± 0.1°

pH	Periodate	Dihydroxy-acetone (dimer)	Curve	(min. ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹ litre)
8.05	3.125 × 10 ⁻³	1.04 × 10 ⁻³	A	1.52
10.45	"	"	B	7.32
11.94	"	"	C	4.72

Second order constant at 40 ± 0.1°

1.90	"	"	D	3.96
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The experimental values of the second order constants and the theoretical values of $\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{--}$ ions are identical in some respect² and that $\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{--}$ ions appeared to be reactive species in this case⁴. The reaction products did not give a precipitate with Mercuric chloride solution showing thereby that no free radical is involved in the reaction.

The reaction can be interpreted to take place between the dihydroxy acetone molecule and $\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{--}$ ions involving no free radical as indicated below

The authors are grateful to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head, Chemistry Department, Jodhpur University and Dr. B. S. Saxena, Head of the Chemistry Department, M. M. H. College, Ghaziabad for providing facilities for work and to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra, Head, Chemistry, Department Rajasthan Univ. Jaipur, for helpful discussions. One of us (P.S.V.) is thankful to U.G.C. for financial assistance.

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Received November 15, 1969
Revised MSS received March 14, 1970

4, C. E. Crouthamel, A. M. Hayes and D. S. Martin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 82.